

Pragmatic Utopian Lighting Design: Classifying a modern architecture movement within the umbrella of sustainable design, and identifying its parallel lighting movement

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Abstract: This paper reviews ideologies of a sustainable design movement called 'Pragmatic Utopia' and presents a parallel lighting movement of the same name. Pragmatic utopia is a term coined by architect Bjarke Ingels of the world-renowned architecture firm Bjarke Ingels Group (BIG) to describe an architectural style that seeks a perfect world through design tempered by reality. The paper aims to identify and learn from what has been observed about pragmatic utopia so as to inspire practicing lighting designers.

Keywords: pragmatic utopia, sustainable lighting design

INTRODUCTION

Pragmatic utopia is a movement that emphasises on socially, environmentally, and economically sustainable design. BIG (Ingels, 2009) argues that architecture is entrenched in two equally unfruitful approaches. First, the utopian approach originating from philosophy, mysticism or a fascination of computer visualizations so detached from reality that they fail to become anything other than eccentric ideas. Second, the pragmatic approach of building well organized but predictable high performing boring boxes. Therefore BIG derived a third approach wedged in the small but very fertile overlap between these two approaches called 'pragmatic utopia.' Semantically, pragmatism and utopianism are two contradictory concepts: pragmatism advocates behaviour dictated by practical consequences than theory or dogma; utopianism describes a perfect world that often conflicts with reality. Based on these definitions, pragmatic utopia is the marriage between a practical approach to reality, and the ideal of trying to create a sustainable life for future generations. While the traditional approach to sustainability is an exclusive approach that settles for a compromising lowest common denominator, pragmatic utopia is an inclusive approach that ties together conflicting differences (Ingels, 2009).

PRAGMATIC UTOPIAN LIGHTING DESIGN – THE FUNDAMENTALS

Pragmatic utopian lighting design (Dugar & Lewis, 2014) fundamentally expands on the current set of criteria for sustainable lighting – social, environmental and economics – by focussing on human (animal) biology and interaction. Socially sustainable lighting will include criteria beyond visual function and performance, and focus on satisfaction, pleasure and delight through greater sensory stimulation (Willey, 2006). Stimulation is a psychological need that increases the satisfaction of performing mundane tasks by increasing attentiveness, reducing fatigue, altering perceptions of time, and promoting a positive outlook from the human perspective by providing visual interest (Dugar, 2016; Winchip, 2005). The social impacts of design are of course driven by architectural concepts. Though more and more, lighting is addressed earlier on projects, and with advancement in research there are real opportunities for lighting to positively influence public space and human health. Additionally, social responsibility entails an interest in the greater good of society by designing spaces with public access that promote positive social interactions for all demographics.

Environmentally sustainable lighting will include criteria beyond stringent energy codes and LEED credits, and focus on human health (Fehrenbacher, 2006). If humans are not exposed to sufficient amounts of light in the right wavelengths at the right time of day, their biological clock becomes desynchronized with the solar day, which may result in a decline in physiological functions, neuro-behavioural performance, and sleep (Brainard, Rollag, & Hanifin, 1997). LED technology provides the opportunity to design with 'dynamic white' electric lighting systems that can shift colour temperature in alignment with daylight (Ellis, Gonzalez, Kratzer, McEachron, & Yeutter, 2013). Paired with well day-lit spaces, these conditions have shown improved recovery time in hospital patients (Cornelissen & Knoop, 2008). Although more conclusive research is needed before circadian lighting can genuinely be implemented with predictable results, the potential for supporting human

health in the built environment is real. The instigation of the WELL design guidelines shows the time has now come for a more human-oriented approach to lighting design.

Economically sustainable lighting will include criteria from two different perspectives. The first is an obligation to discuss openly with architects and owners the potential increase in the initial investment in sustainable systems (luminaires and controls), as well as the projected cost savings and life cycle costs due to a reduction in energy consumption over time. The second perspective focuses on lighting as a sustainable profession (Rea, 2009). Sustainability of the lighting profession will be determined by its ability to define, articulate, and deliver lighting designs that simultaneously meet the needs of the visual environment and preserve the natural environment (Loeffler, 2007).

PRAGMATIC UTOPIAN LIGHTING DESIGN – THE IDEOLOGIES AND THEIR LIGHTING PARALLELS

A varied set of theories and practical project examples in architecture and urban design have been used as an inspiration for identifying some of the core ideologies of pragmatic utopia (Chodikoff, 2008; Dugar, 2016; Ingels, 2009; Zabetas, 2007). Parallels are then drawn to the lighting industry with project examples that reinforce these ideologies.

Ideology # 1 – Methodically riposte nature

The first ideology of pragmatic utopia is to methodically riposte nature. BIG's design proposals for the Rødovre and Escher Towers in Copenhagen are examples of building forms generated as an answer to natural forces. The Rødovre Tower has building forms that maximize daylight and minimize overheating and glare. The towers are oriented towards the sun and the design optimised for passive solar heat gain. Sunlight is also ensured for the terraces of all apartments from morning to evening. Offices, on the other hand, occupy the north facades as they do not need sunlight because of excess heat and glare, but still need diffuse daylight. However, as the east and west facades risk considerable overheating in the summer months, the building volumes lean towards the south. The Escher Tower consists of a building form with three-square towers merged into one so as to withstand vertical stress from gravity loads and horizontal stress from wind loads. The central tower is straight while the two peripheral towers shift location in plan between ground floor and penthouse, causing the volume to flip 90 degrees; thereby providing structural stability. Riposting nature therefore generates structurally impossible-looking architectural forms.

Parallel in lighting # 1

The nexus of health, energy and technology have raised serious issues about the psychophysiological effects of light on the body and the need for natural light in the lit environment for improved functioning of the human biological systems. While it is impossible for electric light to exactly replicate natural light, the intent should be to design balanced luminous environments that are synchronised in the best possible manner with the innate biological systems of all living beings occupying the spaces. The application of the first ideology of methodically riposting nature with appropriate design and technologies can result in lit environments remodelled on nature. The sculptural redesign of Andronikos Hotel on the Mykonos Island by KLab architecture provides an impression that the building has burst forth from the island's natural rocky landscape. Light filtering through the bamboo canes and miniature glass windows, and out from under the furniture generates a sense of serenity and intimacy. The deep blue and pure white colour scheme based on the natural beauty of the Aegean Sea and desert-like landscape respectively has positive biological effects: blue has a calming effect on the endocrine system that secretes hormones directly into the circulatory systems to target distant organs; white has a relieving effect on stress symptoms and positively affects the lymphatic system, stomach and joints. 4000K LED lighting is discreetly integrated into the sculptural forms so as to amplify these colours to their best advantage. Additionally, a small number of 3000K downlights and spotlights add warmth similar to a sunlit space. Advanced lighting control technologies seamlessly interconnect natural and electric light as well as provide user-specific control.

Figure 1. Andronikos Hotel, Mykonos
(Source: Vandoros & Paraskevopoulos 2017)

Ideology # 2 – Enterprisingly utilise resources

The second ideology of pragmatic utopia is to enterprisingly utilise resources. BIG’s design proposals for Little Denmark in Copenhagen and Zira Zero Island in Baku, are examples of where architecture orchestrates the flow of artificial and natural resources. Little Denmark and Zira Zero Island are heated and cooled by heat pumps connected to the surrounding landscape. Solar thermal panels integrated into the architecture create a steady supply of hot water, while photovoltaic panels on strategically located facades and rooftops power daytime functions. Grey and storm water are collected and led to treatment plants to be recycled for irrigation. The solid parts of the wastewater are composted for fertilizer. The wind is harvested through offshore wind farms to provide carbon-neutral power supply. Therefore a whole new range of liberating aesthetics in architecture is triggered where the costs incurred for sustainability can be regarded as an investment rather than an expense.

Parallel in lighting # 2

The emerging trend in the ever-evolving sustainable design arena is to create net-zero energy buildings. While there is a general consensus on the importance of adopting advanced lighting technologies, investment costs, payback periods and reliability are impeding factors that have led to various levels of acceptance of these technologies. The application of the second ideology of enterprisingly utilising available resources to achieve better performance can justify these investments. The Traverso-Vighy Zero Energy Building (TVZEB) in Vicenza is an experimental building that blends seamlessly into the surrounding nature and provides visually designed spaces geared to utilise renewable energy and resources that correspond to its use and context. Conceived as a “daylight funnel”, the building design maximises sunlight exposure during the winter and totally excludes direct radiation during the summer. All south-facing inner surfaces are clad with special mill-finish aluminium with over 90 per cent reflectance that maximises overall daylight use and winter sun reflection deep into the working space. An efficient DMX-controlled LED lighting system with three different colour temperatures (4000K, 6000K and Amber) supplements and emulates the dynamic daylight spectrum that penetrates the building envelope.

Figure 2. Traverso-Vighy Zero Energy Building, Vicenza
(Source: Chemollo & Castagna 2012)

Ideology # 3 – Sensitively acclimate paradoxes

The third ideology of pragmatic utopia is to sensitively acclimate to paradoxes. The Helsingør Hospital designed by BIG is an example of architecture that has adapted to contradictory requirements. Helsingør is designed so that patients are able to enjoy the beautiful views of the surrounding landscape without being exposed to the public. There is clear visibility for the hospital staff to be able to monitor the patients without creating a ‘big-brother’ atmosphere. Although it operates like a hospital with total control to the staff on who would be where and when, it provides an intimate sense of freedom and the safety of a home to its patients. An open-air atrium over two levels brings daylight to the interior from various directions. The result is a prescription of diagnosing architectural paradoxes, which understands the daily dilemmas of users and owners.

Parallel in lighting # 3

A very significant issue within intelligent spaces is lighting that is capable of adapting to future conditions based on user requirements. The application of the third ideology of sensitive acclimation in the form of adaptive lighting with intuitive controls can result in the replacement of fixed lighting with flexible components. The Swarm System from Zumtobel is an adaptive lighting management system configures itself by means of sensors such as ultrasound and light to record the positions of the luminaires in a space, which then enables fast and easy adaptation to changing situations within spaces such as offices, streets or roadways. In a typical office situation during full occupancy, basic room lighting ensures appropriate luminance distribution, while supplementary light allows for individual visual tasks and indirect lighting of the ceiling. In the case of partial occupancy of specific workplaces, reduced basic lighting in these areas minimises energy consumption. Through this mutual communication with each of the luminaires in the vicinity, an intelligent light cloud is formed, creating a pleasant atmosphere in the immediate surroundings based on the available daylight and electric light. In a typical street or roadway lighting situation, when vehicles enter a specific area or zone, the integrated sensors transmit signals to the neighbouring luminaires, which then successively increase the light level, thus accompanying the vehicles. This results in an efficient and energy-saving lighting management system, which

Figure 3. Zumtobel's *Swarm System*
(Source: Zumtobel 2015)

reduces operating costs, provides maximum visual comfort and individuality.

Ideology # 4 – Discreetly integrate history

The fourth ideology of pragmatic utopia is to discreetly integrate history. BIG's design proposal for the Vilnius World Trade Centre 1 is an example of modern architecture integrated with their respective historically significant sites. The challenge when integrating a mixed programme for the Vilnius World Trade Centre 1 into a historically fragile context was how to straddle between architecture and urbanism. Skyscrapers were definitely not an option next to the heritage baroque city of Vilnius. The initial idea of mapping downtown Vilnius onto the site created a series of separate buildings cut off from each other by streets and squares. The pattern was inverted by turning the streets into buildings and the blocks into parks to create a network of

separate functions fused together to form a whole. The building form is like a patch of the baroque city's organic pattern, starting with the conference centre at the centre and various programmes reaching outwards.

Parallel in lighting # 4

The lighting of heritage buildings can become an issue using conventional light sources and luminaires, which generally tend to be too large and cumbersome to be able to integrate with the architectural fabric. The principal task is to highlight the architectural details so that these buildings can be viewed and celebrated after dark. The application of the fourth ideology of discreetly integrating advanced lighting technologies can protect the architectural integrity of these buildings. OVI's lighting design solution for the Rookery building in Chicago more than adequately demonstrates that size and precision are no longer issues for solid-state lighting. Completed in 1888, the 12-storey building's distinctively dark red masonry facades were left unlit making it visually disappear at night. The use of standard luminaires seemed impossible, as every window condition on the building is unique with over 100 irregular ledges. Another critical issue was to prevent harm to the masonry by not penetrating the historic building fabric. A custom miniature 14.4 Watt LED luminaire with a telescopic mounting arm was designed to accommodate different ledge conditions and allow for lockable field conditions and aiming. The luminaires are positioned on every third level to graze the facade and detailing around the window frames with a soft glow. Discreet mounting to the granite windowsills instead of the façade, together with polyurethane feet, minimise direct contact with the historical ledges. The 'Rookery-red' finish of the luminaire blends with the façade, while the micro-optics eliminate glare for the tenants and minimise light

Figure 4. Rookery Building, Chicago
(Source: Sundin & Peiniger 2014)

trespass into the night sky. The overall power consumption for the façade lighting is less than 2.4kW.

Ideology # 5 – Objectively fraternise societies

The fifth ideology of pragmatic utopia is to objectively fraternise societies. The Sjakket Youth Club designed by BIG in working-class Copenhagen neighbourhoods is an example of architecture that has consorted with the social fabric. In a culturally homogeneous population, these neighbourhoods comprise a major population of foreign-born students coming from non-Danish ethnic backgrounds. Social problems such as poverty, unemployment, drug abuse and ghettos have persisted with the immigrant and ethnic minority groups in this area. Thus began the mandate for establishing outlets for creative and physical activities in this potent mixture of youth culture and immigrants. The design process was to refurbish the area without gentrifying its raw beauty and alienating the original occupants. The building uses interesting material palettes that are sampled from the best materials of all the resident cultures so as to reflect the true diversity of the areas. BIG's design proposal for the Slussen in Stockholm is another example where the unique three-dimensional form of the urban space is transformed to accommodate people instead of cars. The urban infrastructure of cars, buses and trains is to be transformed into a social infrastructure to support the free flow of public life from the city to the water. Therefore architecture is evolved from the belief in quality of life and human interaction as the infrastructure for a sustainable city.

Parallel in lighting # 5

Apart from providing visual comfort and safety, the scope of lighting design also involves reviving and rejuvenating urban spaces. Social interaction is an often-neglected yet essential component in such urban design projects. The application of the fifth ideology of objectively fraternising through lighting that affects social interaction can rejuvenate the urban fabric at large. Broken Light is an immersive experience developed by Daglicht & Vorm. The project uses light as art to reflect the fiery past of Katendrecht, a neighbourhood of Rotterdam. Broken Light rejuvenated and transformed the look and feel of Atjehstraat, a street that until a few years ago was rife with crime, by creating a social sculpture. It exists as an interior, cathedral-like space for the street's residents, who literally and figuratively have welcomed it into their neighbourhood. Static and tight beams of light rise up along facades as tall columns, which are balanced by pools of light reflected on the ground. The light motifs, inspired by flowers and birds, look like graffiti from above and are experienced as pools of light and dark by pedestrians. The optical system and luminaires are custom-designed to vary the size, pattern and intensity of the light projections to customise space between windows, creating glare-free street

Figure 5. Broken Light, Rotterdam
(Source: Teunissen, Wilschut & Ijzendoorn 2014)

lighting. The vertical and horizontal projections of light are operated by a single-lamp luminaire mounted on a six-metre high pole. Additional road lighting is provided by a standard luminaire mounted on the same pole by means of an additional bracket.

Ideology # 6 – Imaginatively explore regulations

The sixth ideology of pragmatic utopian design is to imaginatively explore regulations. BIG's design proposals for the Tøjhuset and Battery projects in Copenhagen are examples of architecture that has stretched the limits of building codes. The master plan for these projects called for high-density residential and mixed-use developments. The city building code defines an equation for how tall a building can be, proportionate to its proximity to the nearest neighbours. The ingenious design process applied for both these projects was to establish phantom images of the maximum building envelope by measuring the distance to all neighbouring buildings. The resulting expressive volumes, which comprise additional square metres of space although of abstract origin, were so much more similar to the neighbouring buildings that they were lauded both by the city architects and the clients. Therefore instead of ignoring or complaining about rules and regulations, architecture free from any stylistic straightjacket can be generated within the constraints of rules and regulations.

Parallel in lighting # 6

Adhering to stringent codes and standards is a key issue in the lighting design process, as projects must meet a series of performance requirements. This is typical specifically for renovation projects where older buildings no longer meet the required technical indoor climate, electrical engineering, lighting and safety standards. The sixth principle of imaginatively exploring the regulations can be used as an opportunity to lend existing architecture a new identity through lighting. The exposed concrete architecture of the Kongress am Park convention centre in

Augsburg was over four decades old and in desperate need of a facelift. The building underwent complete renovation, which included the refurbishment of all concrete elements and an up-to-date lighting scheme. The brutally rough and monotonously desolate grey concrete surfaces became an excellent canvas to provide a wide range of striking scenarios using state-of-the-art dynamic LED lighting designed by d-lightvision, a lighting

Figure 6. Kongress am Park Convention Centre, Augsburg

design practice based in Munich/DE. Coloured light is applied to define room depth as well as render the room surfaces subtle eye-catchers. Apart from meeting technical standards for different interior spaces, the renovated lighting atmosphere changes from emotionally driven to sober and practical, depending on how the spaces are used. While the daytime lighting concept is to reveal the form and textural quality of the concrete, the nighttime concept is to render inner sections of the building visible to the outside world. Spectacular compositions of warm and cool colours create interest and suspense, capturing onlookers' attention and inspiring an emotional response.

Ideology # 7 – Opportunistically mutate ideas

The seventh ideology of pragmatic utopian design is to opportunistically mutate ideas. BIG's design proposals for the Clover Block in Copenhagen and the People's Building in Shanghai were competition entries for lost causes. The Clover Block, originally designed as a mega perimeter block of affordable housing around a football field, was then resurrected as a perimeter building to protect the Khalifa Park against extreme desert conditions in Abu Dhabi. The People's Building, originally designed as the Danish Pavilion for the Shanghai Expo, was then scaled up to become a landmark building for the People's Republic of China. Thus there arises a new career path in architecture – overcoming accidental challenges through the mutation and migration of old ideas.

Parallel in lighting # 7

Factors such as the commoditisation, the global macroeconomic situation, energy efficiency regulations and government actions limiting certain profligate uses of energy sources will require lighting professionals to increasingly act as energy and investment advisers besides their normal role as visual environment advisers. The profession itself will thrive when lighting professionals start positively influencing the global market as collaborative advisers for energy savings without sacrificing visual quality. The application of the seventh ideology of opportunistically mutating the lighting professionals' role as advocates for sustainability can help open new markets for their products and services. Lighting service agreements (LSA) that leverage advances in technology and lighting science by bundling in products and services at very little or no delta cost can add value to the lighting professionals' work. For example, an LSA leasing commercial LED lighting would provide threefold benefits: one, tenants would get state-of-the-art equipment without the capital expenditure or risk of a new technology; two, companies leasing the lighting equipment would gain predictable revenue streams with higher gross margins over time; and three, lighting professionals would bring about a flurry of innovations around the purchase paradigm along with significant energy savings.

CONCLUSION

People are fatigued by urban sprawl, degradation of environmental quality, and decaying safety and sociability in their neighborhoods, as the status quo of sustainable design does not seem to be meeting public expectations (Kasperzyk, 1991). As economies and environments continue to evolve and change, careful design and conservation can improve human lives and prepare urban centres for a resilient and positive future. The process of achieving pragmatic utopian lighting design is to first seek a buy-in from the owner and the rest of the team by considering fundamental criteria at project kick-off: socially, environmentally and economically sustainable lighting. Then it is important to establish the primary ideology that is relevant to the project from any of the above-mentioned seven ideologies. Then by applying one ideology, an interconnected chain of ideologies is triggered, which is analogous to the carbon ring: the end result of one ideology leads to the start of another. Finally, a back-check has to be done to evaluate the implementation of the primary ideology at relevant project milestones.

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